

STUDYING DIPLOMACY LEXIS: LINGUISTIC HISTORY OF RHETORIC

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Abstract: *This scientific article gives information about the fact that literary language is the measure and criterion of correct speaking and writing culture, the history of the emergence of rhetoric, the stages of its formation, its role in linguistics, the views of linguists on rhetoric, researches, and diplomacy in the field of international negotiations, in which they can effectively use rhetoric to clearly and clearly express their position, and the art of public speaking began with the speech of sophists in the West and the speech of preachers in the East.*

Key words: *literary language, rhetoric, lexicon of diplomacy, speech, orator, ethos, pathos, logos, sophist, preacher, oratory.*

It is known that language is a mirror of culture, in which not only the real existence that surrounds a person, his real living conditions, but also the social self-awareness of the nation, its mentality, lifestyle, traditions, reflects the national character such as customs, morals, set of values and worldview. Language is a treasure, a chest, a complex of culture. Language is a carrier of culture, it bequeaths the treasure of national culture from ancestors to generations. It is natural for the young generation to learn the rich cultural experience of their ancestors along with their mother tongue [1, P. 394].

Literary language is the measure and criterion of correct speaking and writing of speech culture. Literary language, in fact, is a component of speech culture, and it is a phenomenon that strives for culture. In order to demand speech culture from people, that is, to speak and write correctly, it is necessary to define a tool that can be a tool for such speaking and writing. Such a weapon is literary language.

Today's rapidly growing globalization requires many countries to perfect diplomatic and political lexical units in their native languages in order to clearly and clearly express their position in restoring relations with each other [2, P. 398-399]. "It is known from recent reports that the field of diplomacy is facing some linguistic and didactic difficulties in conducting

international negotiations at a successful level, and as a result, it is facing conflicts such as the escalation of the situation between some countries."

It is a requirement of the time to note that identifying external threats in advance, taking appropriate diplomatic measures against them, expanding trade-economic and investment relations with foreign partner countries, and protecting the rights of compatriots abroad are the main tasks of Uzbek diplomacy [3, P. 33]. .

It should be said that communicative mistakes can cause cultural shock to another person, failure of interpersonal and inter-national communication or serious conflict with so-called "geopolitical consequences".

In this research work, we are talking about the linguistic study of rhetoric as an integral part of the lexicon of diplomacy. After all, today's diplomat should take into account the mentality, outlook, customs, traditions, written and oral sources of the countries and peoples to which he is attached, even their tone of voice and facial expressions. After all, every country has its own national and cultural language [4, P. 2].

Rhetoric (Greek: *rhetorike* - oratory) - the art of speaking; in a broad sense, it is a science of artistic prose. Studying the science of rhetoric, researching its importance in human life has always been relevant. Considering that rhetoric is found in every aspect of life, it is related not only to linguistics, but also to a number of disciplines, such as sociology, politics, cultural studies, pedagogy.

If we look at history, we can see that the beginning of world rhetoric, which has existed for more than 2500 years, is usually associated with ancient civilization. It can be proven that there are some traditions similar to rhetoric in Indian and Chinese cultures. Perhaps rhetoric arose in the depths of various civilizations due to some general laws of human society. Rhetoric went through several stages until it was formed as a separate science. The establishment of democratic institutions in Athens in 510 BC showed the importance of oratory, especially in public service sectors [5, P. 12].

Foundations of theory of speech culture were created in ancient Greece and Rome. The requirements for the speech have been developed. The development of the slavery system, slavery democracy was the main reason. During this period, the development of the state, trade, and court cases raised public speaking to the level of art. In order to become a mature person, mastering the art of public speaking was an

obligation. It is because of this need that the theory of public speaking is created. Its theorists such as Cicero, Demosthenes, Quintilian, and Aristotle flourished. Aristotle's "Rhetoric" was created in 335 AD. In it, the speaker sets the following tasks:

- Comprehensive preparation of the material.
- Determination of material placement plan.
- Mastering the material, correcting speech construction.
- The speaker's study of speech material.
- Expressing the material in words.
- Pronunciation of speech, that is, speech process.

Rhetoric took the form of a systematic science in the III-II centuries BC. This science spread in Rome in the 1st century BC. The word rhetoric basically has two different meanings: 1. The art of oratory and art prose in general in antiquity and later times; theory and art of public speaking, 2. High-flying, tame, but dry, meaningless speech, statement.

There are two types of ancient rhetoric:

- ancient Greek rhetoric (sophists, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Demosthenes);
- ancient Roman rhetoric (Cicero, Quintilian).

There are two major periods in the development of ancient rhetoric that roughly coincide with the two periods in the development of slave-owning democracy:

a) in Greece in the V-IV centuries BC. In Athens - the period from Pericles to Demosthenes;

b) Cicero's time in Rome in the 1st century BC.

A group of teachers, called sophists, began to teach people to speak better and more expressively [6, P. 60]. Sophists received very high fees for lessons, and they considered their acquired knowledge to be wisdom [7, P. 223]. In ancient Greece, there was a class of sophists (from the Greek "sophiste") – "people who are knowledgeable in some field". They were philosophers and professional teachers of philosophy, who developed classical examples of ancient Greek rhetoric. The most famous sophists of ancient Greece: Protagoras, Gorgias, Hippias, Prodicus, Antiphon, Critias, Empedocles.

The sophists believe that the philosophy of life is only their view: man is the measure of all things (Protagoras). Sophists used two tools in rhetoric:

- a) dialectics - the art of thinking, debate, conversation;
- b) rhetoric is the art of persuasion.

The sophists believed that an opponent who mastered both arts could convince any opponent and win the victory of his opinion.

In Rome, masters and teachers of official rhetoric were Greeks. Cicero and Quintilian, great masters of theoretical and practical rhetoric, worked on the basis of the Greek style [8, P. 252]. The foundations of the theory of expressive speech begin with Aristotle's treatise "Rhetoric" [9, P. 3], Corax Syracuse - a person of Sicilian Greek origin was the founder of oratory [8, P. 252], the first orators: Antiphon, Andokides, There are also different views that there were Lucias, Socrates, Isaus, Demosthenes, Lucirgus and other such orators.

Several Greek scientists who made a great contribution to the formation of rhetoric as a science, such as Plato and Aristotle, studied and researched the science separately, and their thoughts and views have not lost their importance even today.

Below we will talk about their views on rhetoric and the development of science.

Plato (428/27 - 348/47 BC) founded his own school (Academy) and was recognized as a master of dialogue and debate by "naturalists", "philosophers" and "rhetorics". His following comments on the art of public speaking are noteworthy:

"... Only when teachers talk about justice, beauty, and benevolence, clarity, perfection, and energy appear in speech" [10, P. 80];

"If someone aims to speak the truth, he should have a good knowledge of just matters" [10, P. 341];

"Each speech should be written like a living thing: it should have a body with head and legs, body and limbs should fit together and fit all" [10, P. 341].

During Plato's time, the opposition between rhetoric and philosophy grew stronger. According to him, rhetoric has no right to be called a science that studies the laws of speech, because the form of speech does not obey general laws and is determined only by the specific content of speech. According to Plato, rhetoric is primarily practical knowledge based on experience rather than learning.

Plato's strict actions against rhetoric led to the increase of the highest level of hostility between rhetoric and philosophy. But this relationship, like the others, could not last long. That's why in the 4th century, there was a tendency to reconcile these two sciences. From the point of view of philosophy, this issue fell upon Aristotle.

Aristotle (384-322 BC) analyzed, summarized and theoretically grounded the Greek achievements in rhetoric. He emphasized rhetoric as the ability to find reliable ways to convince a person with every word. According to Aristotle, the work of rhetoric is not to convince, but to find ways to convince at any time. These problems are described in Aristotle's famous treatise "Rhetoric". This pamphlet consists of three books.

The first book examines the place of rhetoric among other sciences, analyzes the principles that influence listeners, and reveals the essence of oratory. In this, Aristotle talks about the unity of the three components of oratory: the speaker, the subject of speech, the listener (who, according to Aristotle, called "the ultimate goal of everything").

According to Aristotle, a speech is persuasive when the audience perceives the speech to be fair, useful, or pleasant. Any kind of speech is an inevitable unity of *ethos*, *pathos* and *logos*.

Ethos is a moral and philosophical principle. In this case, the relevance of the speech, its acceptance or rejection is in accordance with the moral standards of the listeners.

Pathos is an emotional beginning. A speaker's point is a speech designed for an audience. Here the situation of the speaker, his belief is meant.

Logos is used as a means of verbal and mental speech, as well as to gain the speaker's confidence in order to achieve a logical goal.

The second book deals with the personal characteristics of the speaker, through which he can increase the confidence of his audience and therefore achieve his goal more quickly. According to Aristotle, the characteristics necessary for an orator are: higher education, social activity, a position respected by people, holding a public position, mastering speech, perfect honesty.

Aristotle paid great attention not only to passions, but also to morality. According to him, the speaker himself should experience the passion that he wants to arouse in the audience. For people who are supposed to be public speakers, the qualities that Aristotle emphasized have not lost their importance today, on the contrary, they have gained special importance.

The third book is devoted to issues of styles and speech - compositions (choice of materials, arrangement, oral expression, memorization, speech pronunciation).

In many countries, rhetoric is considered important in the 3 main areas of life: politics, judiciary and religion.

Traditional rhetoric did not fail to influence public speaking in Great Britain. In this country, the Middle Ages were a time when religious oratory flourished and attention to political oratory declined. The most famous orator in England was John Henry Newman, who, while promoting the religion widely, had a great influence on the development of local religious standards in the church. Famous orators of ancient times such as Paul, John Chrysostom, Augustine are among them, Savonarola in the 15th century, Martin Luther and John Calvin by the 16th century. In the 18th century, under the influence of Latin and Greek literature, the art of oratory developed even more in England. During this period, political speech was also considered important, and attention to it increased. The reformation of laws in the 19th century (1832) led to further development of the art of oratory. But in a short time, it turned into a dry political speech, nonsense. By the 1920s, traditional rhetoric lost its scientific value and it was included in the science of stylistics [11, P. 36].

The art of speaking, known as rhetoric in Greece, was called preaching in the East. The art of preaching is an art with a wide social status as the main means of public speaking, scientific and political lectures, debates, debates, propaganda and propaganda. appeared in public and spoke about his politics, the international situation, etc. It is customary to go out in front of people, especially during Friday prayers, Eid, Nowruz holidays, gatherings at the beginning of inter-country war, and other similar days [12, P. 7]. Later, they entrusted this important work to preachers, special people who speak politely, impressively, and can convince [13, P. 6].

In the development of rhetoric in Uzbekistan, the teachings of Sufism, which leads a person to spiritual and moral perfection, also gained great importance. Qazi Eshani (XV-XVI) from Fergana, who is the author of the work called "Key of Words", made a great contribution to the development of rhetoric. He had the ability to convince people, encourage and win any debate [13, P. 16].

Khoja Muyad Mehnagi, Maulana Riyazi, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, Maulana Muin Vaiz Khusravi, Bahauddin Valad, Jalaluddin Rumi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Muhammad Sadiq Kashgari, Abu Nasr Farabi, Kaikovus, Mufti Ziyavuddin Khan Eshan Babakhan Og'li and others were famous figures of their time with the power of words and the art of lively speech [13, P. 17].

At the beginning of the 60s of the 21st century, special attention was paid to mastering the norms of the literary language. After the traditional rhetoric lost its scientific value, it was included in the science "Basics of

speech culture" in higher education institutions. Historical rhetoric had its own way of life. A new life brought him new styles.

Our scientific research work is one of the latest research works related to the cross-sectional study of rhetoric in our country, taking into account that it is partially related to this work, as it is dedicated to the cross-sectional study of the lexicon of diplomacy in French, English and Uzbek languages. We carried out based on the doctor's dissertation of H. Samigova called "A comparative study of the rhetorical aspect of English and Uzbek speech culture".

According to H. Samigova, research on the theory of speech art has been conducted in various languages in linguistics, and the works of scientists who have contributed enough to this field are noteworthy [13, P. 5]. For example, A. Judis focused on researching dialectal features of dialogic rhetoric in English, C.P. Foley studied the characteristics of promises in rhetoric based on factual examples in English, M.M. Hincks researched the theory of rhetoric in English written speech, L.M. Long, A.I. Petons also conducted research on the problems related to the rhetorical aspect of the English language [14, P. 5].

N.A. in Russian linguistics. Cashey, G.M. Yarmarkina, Z.I. Researchers like Kurseva approached rhetoric from the point of view of the Russian language. In Ukrainian Linguistics V.O. Nemchenko, N. Yu. Scholars like Geopgieva methodically analyzed the topic of rhetoric.

In Uzbek linguistics A.H. Aripova paid attention to the study of the types of oratory and the clarification of issues related to the linguistic and methodological tools of the orator's speech. D. Teshabaeva researched modern aspects of speech culture on the example of mass media text, while H. Jalilov, H. Rasulov, S. Svirsky, A.E. Mikhnevich, I.A. Scientists such as Krivelev, N. Mahmudov worked on the topic of the art of speaking of teachers and lecturers. S. Inomkhojaev conducted a research on the historical stages of the Eastern art of oratory. B. Omonov analyzed the skill of political oratory [15, P. 5].

In the doctoral dissertation of H. Samigova, which is considered one of the latest research works on rhetoric in our country, linguistic units related to the phonetic, morphological, lexical and syntactic language levels that serve to increase the effectiveness of dialogic speech in English and Uzbek, dialogic rhetoric in English and Uzbek differences between paraphonetic and parakinetic tools that show the differences and commonalities of languages, linguistic tools that reflect the nationality and commonalities of

dialogic rhetoric in linguistic, cultural and gender aspects, linguistic tools on widely used topics in dialogic rhetoric, according to the level of activity according to their use in speech, language units with positive and negative meanings in dialogic rhetoric in English and Uzbek languages were researched.

Rhetoric has two meanings. The first is a science that studies the basics of public speaking, and the second is a field that scientifically studies any expressive and effective speech.

The dictionary of the modern Russian literary language gives the following definitions of rhetoric:

1. Oratory, oral theory. Research topic, theory of oral speech.
2. Wonderful, beautiful speech, nightingale.

For the existence of two and a half thousand years of rhetoric, hundreds of formulas have been used to define it. Theorists propose three main definition groups:

First, commonly referred to as Greek, defines rhetoric as "the persuasive art" (a central concept in Plato and Aristotle).

The second group of definitions is more related to the Roman civilization. Quintilian gave the clearest formula: rhetoric is "the art of speaking well." Since then, interest in the literary and linguistic part of the text has increased in rhetoric and has become one of the reasons for the crisis of rhetoric.

A third group of definitions from the Middle Ages and early Renaissance describe rhetoric as a "decorative art." The emergence of this group was mainly the result of the second principle - the increase in the aesthetic properties of the word and the spread of the unity of Logos (thought) and expression (language).

In our opinion, rhetoric is a process characteristic of both oral and written speech, and it is closer to pragmatics in terms of its function and influence. Pragmatics is to increase the effectiveness of speech using various stylistic colors, while rhetoric is to deliver this speech beautifully. Usually, the concept of oratory is applied to the owner of a beautiful speech. Here, let's emphasize our thoughts about oratory.

Oratory is a special type of speech, preparing and giving a speech, holding a conversation, etc. In the art of oratory, first of all, attention is paid to the high skill of public speech, the qualitative features of public speaking, skillful mastery of the living word. Oratory is the art of constructing and public speaking to have the desired effect on an audience. Oratory is the

name of a historical, well-known philosophical discipline and academic discipline, which defines the basis of oratory.

Oratory is closely related to any subject. Even the classical philosophers Plato and Aristotle favored speaking in terms of knowledge as a way of knowing and interpreting complex things. Later, F. Bacon classified rhetoric as the art of "communication of knowledge". Oratory has never been the same. Depending on the specific application area, it is historically divided into different types.

Types of oratory (types of public speeches):

- socio-political and political-economic topics, political, diplomatic speech, etc.
- academic-university lecture, scientific report, scientific research, scientific communication;
- prosecution, accusation, speech;
- social and household speech, memorial speech, etc.;
- religious-church - sermon, lecture, etc.

In conclusion, we note that today most people are involved in solving the main problems in the social aspects of politics, diplomacy, economy, education and science. In the conditions of transparency and politicization of society, the individual's ability to self-determine, the words in everyday life, the unique importance of oral speech has increased. In this way, it is not wrong to say that rhetoric becomes one of the subjects that should be studied in every field. After all, communication between individuals occurs in any process of any field. Rhetoric and rhetorical speech are of special importance in the effective conduct of this dialogue.

Rhetoric has two meanings. The first is a science that studies the basics of public speaking, and the second is a field that scientifically studies any expressive and effective speech.

Rhetoric is a process characteristic of both oral and written speech, and it is closer to pragmatics in terms of its function and influence. Pragmatics is to increase the effectiveness of speech using various stylistic colors, while rhetoric is to deliver this speech beautifully. Usually, the concept of oratory is applied to the owner of a beautiful speech.

The art of oratory began in the West with the speech of sophists, and in the East with the speech of preachers. Rhetoric has its own historical stages and is characterized by its formation over time. Although rhetoric is interpreted as public speech, any speech, including dialogic speech, serves as the object of study of rhetoric.

In the system of different languages, dialogic rhetoric is characterized by the fact that it has its own linguistic and cultural aspects and the expression of various linguistic and non-linguistic means. From this point of view, the linguistic and cultural features of rhetoric and the importance of linguistic and non-linguistic tools in it can be comparatively studied in the directions of translation studies, ethnolinguistics and comparative linguistics in related and non-related languages.

The science of speech culture is a unique practical field of linguistics. He teaches ways to make a correct and beautiful speech based on the knowledge gained from the theoretical courses of linguistics. He discusses language, language norms, speech, qualities of speech, speech styles, shortcomings and mistakes that can be encountered in speech, and problems related to pronunciation of speech. Speech culture as a science has its object of examination and tasks. The subject of his investigation is the linguistic construction of speech, norms of literary language and communicative (necessary for communication) qualities of speech. Language norm is a central concept in the theory of speech culture. The main object of study of language culture is the norms of the literary language, and its main task is to eliminate the ambiguities in this norm.

REFERENCES:

1. Khamroev U.S., Diplomatic communication: issues of language, linguoculturology and miscellaneous linguoculturology. Science and innovation. International scientific journal VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5. UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337. P. 394-397. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057553>

2. Khamroev U.S., Diplomacy vocabulary as an object of linguistic research. science and innovation. International scientific journal. VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5. UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337. P. 398-403. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057591>

3. Khamroev U.S., The current state of Uzbek diplomacy: the Samarkand Summit of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. The 27th Republican scientific-practical conference on the topic "Innovative approaches, problems, proposals and solutions in science and education". P. 31-35. www.academiascience.uz

4. Khamroev U.S., A diplomat is a perfect translator in at least two languages: an analysis of euphemic words in written translations. The 40th Republican scientific-practical conference on the topic "Development of

the modern system of education and creative ideas, proposals and solutions towards it". P. 59-61. www.bestpublication.uz

5. Bochkov B.A., Rhetoric: teaching and methodical complex / B.A. Bochkov, S.I. Krasnov. – Ulyanovsk: UVAU GA, 2008. – P.74.

6. Vvedenskaya L.A., Pavlova L.G. Rhetoric and culture. - Rostov-na-Donu: Phoenix, 1998. - P. 223.

7. Nurses V.S., Socrates. - M.: Infra - M - Norma, 1996. - P. 60.

8. Funk and Wagnalls, New Encyclopedia. - USA: Funk and Wagnalls, 1976. V 22. - P. 252.

9. Gabunia Z., Bashieva S., Rhetoric is often a traditional culture. - Nalchik, ELFA, 1993. - P. 3-4.

10. Plato, Selected Works. -M., 1970.- P. 341.

11. Giro P., Horse rhetoric and stylistics// Novoe v zarubezhnoy lingvistike. - M.: Progress, 1980. - P. 35-40.

12. Samigova H., A comparative study of the rhetorical aspect of English and Uzbek speech culture: D.S...dis. autoref. - Tashkent: TSEI, 2017. - P.7.

13. National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 12 volumes. - T.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". State Scientific Publishing House, 2001. J. 2. - P. 6;

14. Judith A, The Genre of Logic and Artifice: Dialectic, Rhetoric, and English Dialogues. – Dissertation for Achieving Ph.D. - Toronto, University of Toronto, 1998. – P. 280.

15. Aripova A.H., Linguistic and stylistic tools of public speaking: Philology. science. name ...dis. - Tashkent: UzRFA, Institute of Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, 2002. – P. 170.

16. Kholikulova G., The methodology of using modern communication technologies in the interpretation of the character of the hero in stage works. -Tashkent, 2015.

17. Khamroev U.S., Promoting the culture of diplomatic speech in teaching the Uzbek language. Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Republican scientific-practical conference on the topic "Importance of the Uzbek language in the 3rd Renaissance". October 20, 2022.